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This bulletin has been prepared in an emergency-response context to evaluate the main disruption points and vulnerabilities in terms of movement within the road-circulation networks of *Porto Alegre's*, *Grande Porto Alegre's*, and *Vale dos Sinos* regions, affected by severe floodings from May 2nd, 2024. Recommendations for short-term (1-5 days) and medium-term (10-20 days) were produced based on the comparative analysis between the road-network systems under normal conditions and the compromised access ways due to the flooding.

ABOUT THE INFORMATION PRODUCED IN THIS BULLETIN

The analysis was developed based on configurational methods designed to address potential changes on movement potentials in the road-circulation network structure caused by extreme events (floods, earthquakes, and structural failures), evaluating their impact at the urban and metropolitan scales (Altafini, Braga, Ugalde 2023; Pezzica, Altafini, Cutini, 2022; Hillier, 2007).

These methods simulate the road-network in pre-and-post-disaster conditions to identify:

- Structural transformations of urban grids caused by the floods.
- The road-elements at risk (based on intersected-based vulnerability to hazards);
- The spatial integrity of the road-system, circulation disruptions and overall performance (given the presence or absence redundancies).

The network models' results are important support instruments guiding decision-making, governance strategies, and urban planning oriented to deal with flooding events at different territorial scales. It addresses changes in the local-regional road accessibility and preferential routes patterns, identifying critical points in the system, as well as the land development trends in vulnerable urban areas. (Altafini, Braga, Ugalde 2023; Pezzica, Altafini, Cutini, 2022; Pezzica, Cutini Bleil de Souza, 2020).

The Three Phases of Emergency Management

For operational and Governance purposes, emergency management is traditionally considered as a sequential process, divided into three phases: **response**, **recovery**, and **preparation** (UNISDR, 2009). This division is instrumental in guiding the production of meaningful information that supports the actions set to be done in each phase. Nevertheless, caution should be exercised when this is used for decision-making as these three phases not only variate in duration (from days to months) but can also be overlapped, with different actions and processes occurring simultaneously.

Considering this, the analyses results were allocated to support different priorities, corresponding to these phases. The following recommendations are proposed:

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RECOMMENDATIONS

Immediate Priorities (1-5 DAYS) – Emergency Response

1. Protect and preserve the access to Porto Alegre through RS-118 at all costs (only operational highway in the system).
2. Maintain and reinforce the road infrastructure to ensure that redundancies to the RS-118 are provided – actions such as building and maintaining the emergency humanitarian corridor – access from the *Av. Castello Branco and Túnel da Conceição*.
3. Guide the Civil Defense actors, the National Guard (Army Forces) and other volunteers involved on the rescue efforts, as well as the affected population, showcasing the key urban routes (described below) which are still available for accessing the emergency shelters and for providing supplies for rescue and assistance.

Preferential routes (see figures 2-11 for more information):

Preferential routes in Porto Alegre:

Emergency Humanitarian Corridor (Túnel da Conceição – Av. Castello Branco)

Oswaldo Aranha Avenue (Connection to Porto Alegre’s city centre)

Baltazar de Oliveira Garcia Avenue (Connection to the RS-118 highway)

Assis Brasil Avenue (Connection to the northern regions of Porto Alegre)

Protásio Alves Avenue (Connection to the eastern regions of Porto Alegre)

Ipiranga Avenue (Connection to the city centre and RS-040 highway)

3rd Perimetral road complex (Connection between northern and southern regions of Porto Alegre)

Avenida do Forte (Connection between RS-040 and RS-118 highways)

Preferential routes in Canoas:

Boqueirão Avenue (Connection to Cachoeirinha and Gravataí municipalities)

Santos Ferreira Avenue (Connection to the Canoas Air Base – logistical hub - Connection to Cachoeirinha municipalities)

BR-116 (Highway connection between southern and northern regions of Canoas)

Preferential routes in Cachoeirinha:

Av. das Indústrias e Av. Papa João XXIII (Connection to BR-290 highway – forms a redundancy connection with the Canoas Air Base).

Preferential routes routes in Gravataí:

Dorival Candido de Oliveira Roadway (Connection to RS-020 highway and the *Vale dos Sinos* region – only preserved high-capacity connection to the region)

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RS-118 highway (Connection between *Vale dos Sinos* region and *Porto Alegre*)
RS-030 highway (Connection to the Coast of Rio Grande do Sul – National access)

Preferential routes towards Vale dos Sinos region:

RS-118 highway (Connection between Gravataí and Esteio municipalities)
RS-020 highway (Connection between Canoas and Taquara municipalities)
RS-239 highway (Connection between Novo Hamburgo and Taquara municipalities)
Henrique Closs Road (Connection to *Vale dos Sinos* region towards *Santa Tecla* and *Lomba Grande* neighbourhoods - Redundancy of RS-020)

Short-Term priorities (1-20 DAYS) - Early Recovery

The post-disaster recovery, which has a longer implementation timeframe than the emergency response, should frame action priorities in alignment with the *Building Back Better* principles, disposed by the United Nations Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction – Priority 4 (UNDRR, 2015).

In this phase, the conditions of accessibility to key urban services, such as shelters, hospitals, schools, food and donation suppliers, fire brigade stations, plus other facilities such as logistical hubs, water treatment and pumping stations must be prioritized. Hence, configurational models depicting the patterns of movement (relative accessibility and the preferential routes) can be overlaid to the location of these services to identify the places of foremost action in terms of road deobstruction, repair or reconstruction. This allows Civil Defense service teams, medics, engineers, volunteers, and the general population to access these facilities again, promoting the gradual restoration of the city life towards normal, pre-disaster, conditions.

Medium-Term priorities (MONTHS) - Recovery and Preparation

The disaster recovery processes should also consider a medium-term perspective, based on the vulnerability analysis of critical road-access points and essential urban facilities, plus on a reevaluation of the flood hazards and emergency-response systems within the affected urbanized areas. The interruptions verified on the metropolitan network should be considered in order to support future solutions for increasing the redundancy and resilience of the urban-regional road-circulation system (Pezzica, Altafini & Cutini, 2022; Pezzica 2023; Altafini, et al, 2023). Configurational models can contribute to these processes, informing strategies for recovery, preparation, prevention, and mitigation. The use of techniques such as those presented here for the development of future scenarios requires an evolving disaster perspective, which includes producing information to support both the operationalization of effective responses and for the construction and reconstruction of road infrastructure, locating services, and housing for displaced persons (Pezzica, Cutini, Bleil de Souza, 2020).

ANALYSIS RESULTS

The context:

In normal conditions, Porto Alegre's Metropolitan Region (PAMR) road-circulation network relies on the mobility axes comprised by the national highways: BR-116, BR-290, and BR-448.

Those constitute the **main connections** between the state capital, *Porto Alegre*, its Greater Region (comprised by the municipalities of *Alvorada*, *Cachoeirinha*, *Canoas*, *Gravataí* and *Viamão*); the *Vale dos Sinos*, region (which has, as main municipalities, Novo Hamburgo and São Leopoldo); as well as towards the municipalities of Eldorado do Sul and Guaíba in the west bank of the Guaíba lake.

Moreover, those highways also connect Porto Alegre with Rio Grande do Sul's inner and coastal areas, respectively to the southwest and east, as well as the remainder of Brazil, in the north.

Other axes, comprised by national and state highways are important as **secondary connections** for interurban mobility within the regions, also providing redundancies for the regional system, including the BR-386, RS-118, RS-240, and RS-020. Further regional axes such as RS-030, RS-040 state highways, connect Porto Alegre to the coast and provide redundancies for the BR-290.

The **main accesses to the city of Porto Alegre**, within its urban area, are through seven points¹:

- *Túnel da Conceição* – a tunnel that connects to the *Av. Castello Branco*, the urban extension of the BR-290 (Freeway) – provides direct access to the City Centre;
- *Av. Sertório* – accessed through the *Guaíba* lake movable bridge) from the BR-290 – provides connection from the municipalities of *Eldorado do Sul* and *Guaíba*;
- *Av. dos Estados* – that provides access to the *Salgado Filho* International Airport, through the BR-116, and to *Canoas* municipality.
- *Av. Assis Brasil* – through the BR-290, connects to the municipalities of *Cachoeirinha* and *Gravataí*;
- *Av. Senador Salgado Filho / Av. Protásio Alves / RS-040* – connecting to the municipality of *Viamão*;
- *Av. Baltazar de Oliveira Garcia*, connecting to RS-118 through the municipality of *Alvorada*.

A significant portion of the road network in Porto Alegre and the Metropolitan Region is set in the basins of four important rivers that cross the State of Rio Grande do Sul: (*Cai*, *Sinos*, *Jacuí*, and *Gravataí*); as well as along the shores of Guaíba Lake, making it **rather susceptible to flooding events**. Figures 1 and 2 provide a general overview of the system and its road hierarchy:

¹ Please note that the abbreviation "Av." is used to refer an *Avenida*, the Portuguese translation of Avenue – an arterial urban road the abbreviation was not translated, since it misrepresent local road names.

Figure 1 – Porto Alegre’s Metropolitan Region (PAMR) basins system and road-circulation network.

Four regions of interest are highlighted in figure 2 and in the subsequent figures. Those regions were selected based on their importance in road connectivity in the Metropolitan Region of Porto

Alegre (PAMR): (a) the intersection region of RS 290 with RS 118; (b) BR 116 in São Leopoldo; (c) RS 240 in Montenegro; and (d) RS 290 and the emergency humanitarian corridor – constructed as an early response to the flooded city centre connection.

Figure 2 – Porto Alegre’s Metropolitan Region (PAMR) road-circulation network hierarchies. In the ampliations, the four interest areas highlighted.

Heavy rains that affected the Rio Grande do Sul state between April 27th and May 2nd, 2024 and caused a flooding event in Porto Alegre's Metropolitan Region that peaked on May 6th, reaching a water column level of 5.33 meters on the Guaíba lake, registered at the Mauá Pier in Porto Alegre².

Several sections of the road system were interrupted by the flooding from both Lake Guaíba and its direct tributaries (*Caí, Sinos, Jacuí, and Gravataí* rivers) in the days between May 2nd and May 6th. The flooding situation remained relatively unchanged until May 8th, when images from the Sentinel-2 satellite (ESA) of the European Copernicus Earth Observation Program enabled the monitoring and validation of the flood extent³. This validation process was conducted by a multidisciplinary team with collaborators from various sectors of the Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul (UFRGS) and external volunteer researchers (Possantti et al., 2024).

Figures 3 and 4 illustrate the extent of the maximum flooded area (May 6th – May 8th reference), which is overlaid and intersected to the road-circulation network. The removal of the inaccessible sections allowed the visualization of the system conditions after interruption, as well as its evolution based on the early actions for promoting accessibility. Moreover, it is showcased its division into three distinct regions (Figure 5), identified as: *Greater Porto Alegre* and *Vale dos Sinos* region (in green) - affected by the *Gravataí* and *Sinos* rivers, as well as the Guaíba lake; *Montenegro-Triunfo* (in yellow) – affected mainly by the *Caí* river; and *Eldorado do Sul-Guaíba* (in red) – affected by the *Jacuí* river and by the *Guaíba* lake.

Initially, the flooding caused the partial collapse of the road-circulation network interconnecting Porto Alegre's Metropolitan Region (PAMR), through the severance of five of the seven main routes to access Porto Alegre. This compromised the connections with the Greater Porto Alegre region to the north (*Canoas, Cachoeirinha, and Gravataí*), as it rendered much of the BR-290 inaccessible, even though the highway itself, being set in an elevated position with respect to its surroundings, was unaffected. The partial blockages in *Canoas*, and in *São Leopoldo* (BR-116) caused further points of system disconnection.

Due to the passage of water through the Mauá Pier Wall, which compromised Porto Alegre's flood control systems, the central area was also flooded, severing the access to the BR-290 through *Av. Castello Branco* and the *Túnel da Conceição*. This further reduced the overall redundancy of the system. Porto Alegre, after May 6th, (Figure 3) remained accessible through two routes: the *Av. Baltazar de Oliveira Garcia*, and its linkage to the RS-118 (Alvorada), which maintained Porto Alegre's access to the rest of *Greater Porto Alegre* and the *Vale dos Sinos*

² The up-to-date progression of the water column level and the flooding quotas (3m and 6m) and estimations for the flooding evolution can be verified through the following link: [Rio Grande do Sul | 2024](#)

³ After May 8th, the waters receded to below 5 meters, however, rainfall from May 12th to May 17th caused the waters to again breach the 5-meter threshold.

region, and through RS-040 at *Viamão*, which ensured a second redundancy of access to the coast. Nevertheless, both routes soon became overburdened by the increased movement.

Figure 3 – Road-system conditions after the flood in the May 2th, 2024. (Based on the May 6th-8th, 2024 verified flooding extents)

From May 10th, the Humanitarian Emergency Corridor (Figure 4) – a relief access – was set in operation to reconnect Porto Alegre’s city centre to the highway network. It established a linkage from the *Túnel da Conceição* to the *Av. Castello Branco* and the BR-290.

Figure 4 – Road-system conditions after the flood in the May 10th, 2024; humanitarian emergency corridor open for traffic. (Based on the May 6th-8th, 2024 verified flooding extents)

Figure 5 – The severance of the road-systems after the flood in the May 2th, 2024; (Based on the May 6th-8th, 2024 verified flooding extents)

Reestablishing this connection is expected to allow for improved accessibility conditions between *Canoas* and *Porto Alegre*, providing a shorter route to access *Canoas* airbase, where a logistical

hub was established for receiving relief supplies coming through airlift from the rest of Brazil. However, the connection remained **extremely fragile**, with few redundancies, therefore being still at risk since sections of BR-116 and BR-290 were affected by floodings and blockages at some points. In that regard, the only stable connection continued to be through the RS-118.

Figure 6 – Numbers for the road-network: total number of elements, ratio between operational and flooded road-elements.

Considering this overview, characterizing the PAMR system under normal conditions, and with the interruptions caused by the flooding, configurational analyses were conducted to obtain the results depicting the network patterns of **Relative Accessibility** (Normalized Angular Integration - NAIN) (Figures 7, 8, 9 and 10) and the **Preferential Routes** within the area (Normalized Angular Choice - NACH) (Figures 11, 12, 13, and 14).

Results for Relative Accessibility (NAIN)

Relative Accessibility, modelled through the Normalized Angular Integration (NAIN), indicates the **movement potentials (To-Movement) within a road-element (defined as a network node)**. It demonstrates how topologically accessible/reachable – or central – a road-element is in relation to all others, considering the shortest paths from one element to all others in the system.

The NAIN measure showcases the overall relative accessibility patterns in normal conditions and how they are **preserved or disrupted** by interruptions caused by floodings – providing an indication of which areas will **concentrate** more movement and which areas are **segregated** from the system due to a lack of accessibility. A comparison between normal and flooded states also allows to reflect on which road-elements are **central** to preserve global accesses.

In terms of visualization, the established convention assumes that road-elements coloured in **cool tones (blue-green-yellow)** which indicate low NAIN values – meaning **they concentrate less movement** of pedestrians and vehicles (low accessibility). On the other hand, road-elements

coloured in **warm tones (yellow-orange-red)** correspond to high NAIN values, meaning that they **concentrate more movement** due to its overall higher accessibility within the system. Thus, they are central for the functioning of urban traffic.

Figure 7 – Road-circulation network patterns of relative accessibility (NAIN-Rn). System under normal conditions.

Segments in **red** correspond to the so-called *accessibility/integration core*, being elements with the highest centrality – importance in terms of **to-movement**.

Figure 8 – Road-circulation network patterns of relative accessibility (NAIN-Rn). System conditions considering the flood in the May 2th, 2024; (Based on the May 6th-8th, 2024 verified flooding extents)

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The interruption of road-elements due to the flooding caused a **significant shift** in PAMR's system relative accessibility patterns, when confronted with the system in normal conditions (Figure 7).

Places with **high movement potentials**, such as Porto Alegre's city centre and *Canoas'* BR-116, (region "d" in Figures 7 and 8) **lost accessibility**, while others, such as Gravataí (as in region "a", in Figure 7 and 8) **now concentrate all the movement potentials** due to the interruptions, effectively becoming the regional "accessibility cores".

These overall changes are to be **communicated** to early responders and to the general population to provide information when choosing routes or planning outbound routes, as places that display high NAIN values will naturally concentrate movements, leading to **tendencies of congestion**. Therefore, relative accessibility can guide temporary adjustments to traffic control and signage, to avoid such congestion, and mitigating its impacts on the movements of emergency vehicles, especially the ambulance service (SAMU). Moreover, overlaid to the position of urban equipment (such as shelters and hospitals), it can give a dimension of which of them are in a better position in terms of accessibility – thus that tend to be **more used** by the local population.

Overall, the models indicate the **near collapse** of the road-network in terms of its *relative accessibility* within the *Greater Porto Alegre* region upon the floodings, which is sustained only by the road-elements that comprise the RS-118 (Figure 8, "a"). Despite this, the accessibility conditions within Porto Alegre, *Alvorada*, *Viamão*, *Cachoeirinha*, and *Gravataí* remain stable, with more significant interruptions in the northern area of the Capital and the western area of Canoas. However, these are areas susceptible to local flooding and temporary interruptions.

Accessibility from the *Greater Porto Alegre* to the *Vale dos Sinos* region, however, **is significantly compromised**, with the interruption of the BR-116 in several points – above all at the *Rio dos Sinos* bridge (Figure 8, "b"). Access to this region is maintained through the RS-020, towards the municipalities of Taquara and Parobé, followed by the RS-239, which greatly increases the available shortest paths distance and contributes to its overall segregation.

The road-circulation network was interrupted in several points towards the *Eldorado do Sul-Guaíba* and *Montenegro-Triunfo* regions rendering them **temporarily isolated** from Greater Porto Alegre system, thus forming in those areas local road-network systems with local patterns of relative accessibility (Figure 8). Such local patterns, however, can still be useful for planning emergency relief at urban level, after the establishment of waterway accesses, especially in the case of *Eldorado do Sul-Guaíba*. Access to Montenegro-Triunfo region is gradually being restored by Civil Defense and should be considered in future iterations of the model.

Since the road-elements comprising the RS-118 (Figure 8, region "a") correspond to the only operational linkage that maintains cohesion in the Greater Porto Alegre region, it is recommended that it is protected at all costs, to avoid the risk of a general accessibility collapse. A simulation considering this possibility is shown in the Figure 9. Moreover, the establishment of the emergency humanitarian corridor changes greatly the patterns of *relative accessibility*, towards a system that more closely resembles the normal conditions (Figure 10).

Figure 9 – Road-circulation network patterns of relative accessibility (NAIN-Rn). System conditions considering the May 2nd conditions and the flood and interruption of the RS-118; (Based on the May 6th-8th, 2024 verified flooding extents)

Figure 10 - Road-circulation network patterns of relative accessibility (NAIN-Rn). System conditions considering the May 10nd conditions with the humanitarian emergency corridor open for traffic; (Based on the May 6th-8th, 2024 verified flooding extents)

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With the severance of the RS-118 road-elements, the Greater Porto Alegre area would split into **two road-networks** (Figure 9): the northern system, which comprises the *Canoas-Vale dos Sinos* region, which has the northern part of RS-118 as its “accessibility core”; and the southern system, comprising the *Porto Alegre-Alvorada-Viamão* conurbation. Both road-networks would be only connected through the BR-101, near Rio Grande do Sul’s Coast. This highway establishes the **only link** between the BR-290 to the RS-040 and requires a detour of more than 170km to be accessed.

The conditions of accessibility in the Metropolitan Region **tend to improve**, when considering the emergency access established through the **humanitarian corridor** (region “d, Figure 10), which created another – **albeit fragile** – redundancy in conjunction with the RS-118. The connection between Porto Alegre’s city centre to the BR-116, through the BR-290, **shifts the accessibility core** within Porto Alegre and **facilitates access** towards the Capital – even when considering its inner neighbourhoods – from the airbase in Canoas, thus favouring relief efforts. **Periodic checks should be performed in these routes, being recommended due to the possibilities of interruption of BR-116 (flooding) and BR-290 (landslides).**

Results for the hierarchy of Preferential Routes:

The Preferential Routes hierarchies, modelled through Normalized Angular Choice (NACH), indicates the **probability of a road-element (defined as a network node) to be travelled by** (through-movement), considering the shortest paths from this road-element to reach all other elements in the system. It informs a “route choice hierarchy”, in which, depending on the road-network configuration, a road is more chosen for travelling, therefore tends to have a **higher or lower flow probabilities**. In comparing the systems under normal and flooded conditions, it provides an idea of where the general redundancies in the system are located, as those tend to be intertwined with the preferential routes.

The results for (NACH R_n) reinforce the trends verified for the of the **near collapse** of the metropolitan region's road network, also highlighting the road-elements that maintain functional regional connections. RS-118, again, appears as the only connecting route sustaining the flows between Porto Alegre and the northern places in the Metropolitan region, reinforcing its importance (Figures 9, 10, and 11).

In terms of visualization, the established convention assumes that road-elements coloured in **cool tones (blue-green-yellow)** which indicate low NACH values – meaning **they are in a lower hierarchy, thus have lower flow probabilities** of pedestrians and vehicles passing through. On the other hand, road-elements coloured in **warm tones (yellow-orange-red)** correspond to high NACH values, meaning that they have a higher hierarchy of choice within the system. Thus, they are central for the functioning of urban traffic between origins and destinations. Segments in **red** correspond to the so-called *preferential routes*, being road-elements with the highest centrality – importance in terms of **through-movement**.

Figure 11 - Road-circulation network hierarchies of preferential routes (NACH-Rn). System under normal conditions.

Under normal conditions, the system is structured along two major axes of preferential routes, one in the **north-south direction**, towards the *Vale dos Sinos* region through the BR-116, and the other in the **east-west direction**, through BR-290 (Figure 11, region “d”), connecting the inner

state municipalities to Rio Grande do Sul's coast. With the interruption of the BR-116 at several points (figure 12, as well as the interruption of its main redundancy, the BR-448, the *Vale dos Sinos* region remains only with the RS-020 – one of its redundancies towards the southeast – as the preferred route, directing flows to the northeast of the region towards the municipalities of Taquara and Parobé (Figure 12, region “b”). In this context, RS-239 becomes crucial for flows towards the municipalities of *Vale dos Sinos*.

In the event of a multiple point interruption, such as the caused by flooding from May 2nd to May 8th, which severed the connections towards the city centre, the BR-290 fails to fulfil its role as the “structural through-movement route” for Porto Alegre and the metropolitan region (Figure 12).

With the severance of the exits through the *Túnel da Conceição – Av. Castello Branco*; through the Av. Sertório, the Av. dos Estados and the Av. Assis Brasil (Figure 12, region “d”), the BR-290 role is assumed by the RS-118, which becomes the **only preferential route** available to cross the system.

It is important to highlight the role of primary urban roads in structuring internal flows within municipalities. In Porto Alegre, this role is played by the: Av. Assis Brasil, Av. Protásio Alves, Av. Osvaldo Aranha, Av. Baltazar de Oliveira Garcia, Av. Ipiranga, and the complex of avenues that form the 3rd Perimetral Road; those structure **the flows within the city and remain – mostly – operational**.

In *Canoas*, this role is provided by the Av. Boqueirão and Av. Santos Ferreira (an important connection to *Canoas'* airbase); In Cachoeirinha, this role is assumed by the Av. das Indústrias, due to the disconnection caused by floodings in Porto Alegre's exit through the Av. Assis Brasil. Similarly, the Dorival Cândido de Oliveira Road in Gravataí becomes an option along with its continuation, RS-030, for aid coming from the coast and as redundancy to BR-290, provided that the exit via Av. das Indústrias (Av. Papa João XXIII) in Cachoeirinha is maintained.

The situation in the *Vale dos Sinos* region is, however, **more critical**, as the BR-116, which provides the through-movement options within those urban areas and towards the Greater Porto Alegre region is interrupted. Therefore, the **hierarchy changes towards a localised exchange of flows between Novo Hamburgo and the eastwards Taquara municipality**.

Again, a hypothetical **interruption of RS-118** is simulated to analyse its potential impacts on the system (Figure 11). In this case, although the result would be minimal changes to the internal structure of preferential routes—which tend to be maintained—it would also cause the complete separation of flows between the *Porto Alegre-Alvorada-Viamão*, conurbation and the rest of Greater Porto Alegre in the north (Figure 11, Figure 13).

Figura 12 - Road-circulation network hierarchies of preferential routes (NACH-Rn). System conditions considering the flood in the May 2th, 2024; (Based on the May 6th-8th, 2024 verified flooding extents)

Figure 13 - Road-circulation network hierarchies of preferential routes (NACH-Rn). System conditions considering the May 2nd conditions and the flood and interruption of the RS-118; (Based on the May 6th-8th, 2024 verified flooding extents)

Figura 14 - Road-circulation network hierarchies of preferential routes (NACH-Rn). System conditions considering the May 10nd conditions with the humanitarian emergency corridor open for traffic; (Based on the May 6th-8th, 2024 verified flooding extents).

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In such conditions, the linkage provided by the BR-101, between the BR-290 and the RS-040 would become the most important – and now only – regional redundancy within the system. Such situation would be particularly **problematic for Porto Alegre**, as national aid efforts have the airbase in Canoas as their logistical centre, due to the flooding of the *Salgado Filho* International Airport runway.

On the other hand, the presence of the Humanitarian Corridor (Figure 14) provides the road-network with a crucial redundancy and enables the use of both BR-116 and BR-290, **recovering part of the preferential routes' hierarchies within the Metropolitan Region, being also important for response and relief actions provided from outside the state.**

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